

The Television Morning News for Thai Undergraduate Students: Information Exposure, Uses and Gratifications

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Abstract—The purposes of the study are to study and to investigate the relationship among exposure, uses and gratifications of television morning news among undergraduate students in Bangkok. This study also compares differences in information exposure, uses and gratifications of television morning news among these students.

The research methodology employed a questionnaire as a quantitative method. The respondents were undergraduate students at public and private universities in Bangkok. Totally, 400 usable questionnaires were received. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used in data analysis.

The results indicated that information exposure of undergraduate students in Bangkok was at a high level. Students' uses and gratifications were also at high level. Information exposure was positively correlated with uses and gratifications. Uses of information were positively correlated with satisfaction with information. The results also showed that students with differences in sex and type of university were not significantly different in information exposure, and uses and gratifications.

Keywords—Television Morning News, Information Exposure, Uses and Gratifications.

I. INTRODUCTION

COMMUNICATION is important and closely relative with society. Communication is the bond of society and is a relevant factor with the social process continuously. The evolution of society, since the beginning of time to the present day, has always relied on communication and will continue to do so in the future. We might be able to say that society was created by communication, existing by communication and as society continues to develop will need communication as a key tool unavoidably. Without communication, society members would lack information and data about development and would not be able to change or adjust the knowledge of modern people, and most of society would not be developed [1].

Stepping into the era of information Technology, society influences all regions around the world. It is the era of the scientific and technological advancement is highly topped by all the knowledge. There are communicational and transportation communications that allow people to receive news of current events quickly and conveniently no matter where they live in the world. As such information has become a completely significant factor for human beings.

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In the era of information and data, the new society is filled with the information that mostly is complicated. To receive the information from one's direct experience might not be enough anymore, so to get the information through mediated experience has become the important factor for the social learning process [2]. Media represents a major source of information. No one can deny that the media is influential and plays a major role in everyone's daily life. This is especially true for Thailand as a developing country. As such the population is searching and opening up for more information to keep up with the changes in the situation from outside sources. Benefiting from the data and information of worldwide media has become increasingly important.

The media acts as a "Gatekeeper" of its society by selecting the important news titles or setting agendas for the eyes of public. The media plays the big role in choosing or not choosing to present information to people. This will affect the public's perspective to agree whether one's topic or point of view is significant. This is also for the society or the public to realize the significance of the information presented to them and bring the topics for discussion or comments.

Television is regarded as a very popular media for the audience because the audience can both see the pictures and hear the sound. It is very easy to perceive and to understand. The National Statistics Office 2008 survey about mass media (radio, TV, newspapers) showed that of the country's population aged 6 years and over: 37.3% read a newspaper, 42.8% listened to the radio, and 94.5% watched television [3]. This shows that almost everyone watches television. Therefore, television has become a necessity for daily life. Almost all households have a television to watch. Television is a medium in which people receive information more than others, making a television program play a major role in the society.

Almost every country focuses on the morning news as they are considered the programs that benefit its people directly. The morning news program, therefore, is an essential program that every television channel has to provide to benefit society. Generally, the news program is always aired at prime time; the time where the largest audiences watch television. This is to guarantee that the information will be delivered to the people in order that the people will receive more additional knowledge from the systematic learning. Media exposure is like the non-stop lifetime education that people can get the knowledge to benefit their daily lives and to develop the society respectively.

Television Morning News is very important for people's daily life. Before people leave for work or to do any activity; they need to seek information in order to survive, and know as much as others in society. Our society is full of competition in many aspects. Those who know more (more current) information have an advantage over those who do not and can start the new day being up to date with the world of learning, which is relevant to the theory of the Knowledge-based Society. People need to know up-to-date information all the time in order to apply the knowledge for themselves and society respectively.

In conclusion, this study is aimed to study groups of undergraduate students who watch the television morning news to see how much they apply the information after watching it; also, to study the gratifications towards the TV morning news. This study result can hopefully be used to develop the TV morning news to be more qualified and to benefit and suit the needs of people.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Media Exposure Concept

News and information is necessary for the daily activities of people. As humans are social animals, so it is necessary to exchange news, knowledge and each other's experience. Therefore, news is an important factor to be used in making decisions. Especially when people have a problem, the more we are unsure about one topic, the more the news becomes influential to us.

Rogers and Svenning [4] studied and expanded the idea of media exposure by adding more definition that the media includes newspaper, movies, radio, magazines, and television. With this, the 2 measuring indexes of definition are the frequency of media exposure, period of time, and the amount of the media when exposed.

The media exposure from the media will have the different criteria according to one's experience, needs, beliefs, attitudes, feelings, environment, and other reasons. These selective processes act as a filter for our information perception. These processes are [5]:

1. Selective Exposure or Selective Attention

The information receiver usually chooses to be interested or media exposed from the source that can support the current attitude and try to avoid the information that doesn't support their own idea because to get the information that doesn't support one's current attitude will cause the mentally imbalanced condition called Cognitive Dissonance. Human beings might reduce this imbalanced state by changing attitudes, knowledge, expressive behaviors or selecting the information that suits their own ideas.

2. Selective Perception or Selective Interpretation

When a person receives information, the receiver will select or interpret that information according to their attitude, experience, belief, need, expectation, motivation, and even their current physical or emotional condition.

3. Selective Retention

A person will select to memorize pieces of information that are relevant to their interest, needs, and attitude and tend to forget the parts that they are not interested in or disagree with. As such, the selected choice of information will happen along with the selective retention and the selective perception which was the step that happened before. From the 3 selective processes of human beings, they can be shown in the Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 The 3 selective processes of human beings

McCombs and Becker [6] mentioned that people require media exposure to respond to 4 needs, which are:

1. To know about the situations (Surveillance) by following the movements and observing things from the mass media in order to know situations and to be up to date, and realize what is important to know.
2. To help make decisions, particularly decisions about daily life. Media exposure enables a person to set his own comment to conditions or situations around them.
3. Discussion: media exposure provides data to a person and allows them to have information to discuss with others.
4. Participation, to perceive and participate in events and all happening possibilities in society.

In addition, Schramm [7] has stated that the principals of media exposure also depends on the effort factors that they should be least and to get the most benefits which can be shown in the formula of information selection as "Information Selection = Expectation / Spent effort". This formula can be used to illustrate a person's tendency to select the information that takes least effort to obtain (for example nearby information) and benefit one's self. However, sometimes this formula needs other factors to be considered too, for example, experience, background, and environment.

From the media exposure idea, it shows that in the current fast-changing condition of society, media exposure is an important factor in daily life to respond to human needs. Especially in the highly competitive society like nowadays, people need the information to make decisions and solve problems. The faster information is received, the more advantages a person has.

B. Uses and Gratifications Theory

Uses and gratifications Theory is the consequences from the social and psychological process of the media consumer. The explanation is that apart from the 5 basic needs as Maslow [8] stated Physiological Needs; Security Needs, Love Needs, Self-Esteem Needs, and Self-Actualization Needs, human beings

still want another need. It is the need to have knowledge, and understanding about the environment. This need is an important motivator that human beings have learnt from living together in society. The study under this concept idea is therefore acceptable that human beings deliberately search for information from the media without being forced to read, watch, or listen. Human beings are able to choose, or avoid the information if they have purposes or targets in using the mass media.

Katz, Blumer, and Gurevitch [9] explained that each person who receives information has a different social and mental status. Therefore they have different levels of needs of knowledge, understanding of themselves and society, and needs of entertainment. This concerns the news source or the mass media if they could satisfy these different needs. Different media are also presented in different forms which can reach the expected satisfaction or the unexpected consequences. They also explained about the study methods of the benefits and satisfactions that it is the study about (1) the social and mental status that causes (2) the needs of people that cause (3) the expectation from the mass media that lead to (4) the different forms of media exposure which cause (5) the expected satisfaction and (6) the following consequences which might not be the expected results. All of these factors can be shown as in the model as follows:

Fig. 2 Model of the information receiving process in mass communication

The model illustrates the information receiving process in mass communication and the usage of mass communication by individuals or groups of people. This shows that the mass media consuming option depends on the needs or the motivations of the information receiver. Each individual has specific purposes, intention, and needs of uses to respond to his satisfaction by the different reasons. Consequently, the

media's importance for each individual is different and the satisfaction from the media uses will also vary.

McCombs and Becker said that a person uses the media to respond to needs as follows:

1. Surveillance by following and observing the movements from the media in order to be updated with situations, to be up to date and to know what matters for the learning.
2. Decision especially the decisions making of the aspects related to the daily life. The media exposure enables people to define his own comments towards the state or the situations around.
3. Discussions, The media exposure provides people with data and makes them have information to have a conversation or a discussion.
4. Participating in all happening events or ongoing situations in the society.
5. Reinforcement, to add up or support the happened decisions.
6. Entertaining and Relaxing

However, Kippax and Murray [10] added up about the perceptions of the media's benefits by studying the relationship between media use and gratification gained from that media. The study shows that the audience has the different levels of gratifications as below:

1. Population factors for example; age, education, occupation act as factors for selection of media and perception of the media.
2. Highly educated people will choose more various kinds of media than the less educated.
3. Television is a popular form of media as the audience group agrees that it is the useful media that gives much information that the general population is interested in.
4. Most target groups have purposes in using media, and understand the use of the media.

It can be concluded that the needs of media usage have a relationship with the perception of the use of the media. It also includes the personal factor which influences the media use for the gratifications as the theory that focuses the audience in the communication process. The audience will select the media that is useful and can respond to their needs. To use this theory to refer to this study is to answer the question whether the students' group, who are of mixed gender, from different educational institutes in Bangkok (public and private universities) use the information from the television morning news differently and how.

The theoretical background leads to the following hypotheses:

- H1. Information exposure of television morning news among undergraduate students in Bangkok is related to uses and gratifications of television morning news.
- H2. Uses of information are related to gratifications of television morning news.
- H3. Differences in sex and type of university will reveal differences in information exposure, uses and gratifications of television morning news.

III. METHODOLOGY

This study employed a self-administered questionnaire to collect data from undergraduate students in Bangkok. According to Rubin, Rubin, and Piele [11], survey research employing questionnaires is an appropriate way to collect data from large numbers of people and seeks to explain people's current views surrounding an issue.

A. Population and Sample

The populations of this study are undergraduate students who are studying in public or private universities in Bangkok. Currently, there are 23 public universities and 16 private universities in Bangkok [12]. The minimum sample size required for the study is 176. The sample size was determined using G*Power Software based on the use of Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient and a univariate t-test in data analysis [13], with approximately 80% power to reject the null hypothesis at the .05 significance level for medium effect size. In social science research, a medium effect size is sufficient to achieve acceptable power [14]. Finally, the researcher collected data from 400 participants because of a concern about receiving a low response rate and to ensure the statistical power. The sample is consisted of 41.5% men and 58.5% women. 45% is students from public universities while 55% is from private universities.

B. Measures and Procedures

To examine the hypotheses, the respondents were asked the questions regarding how often they watch the television morning news. The respondents were also asked to score uses and gratifications from television morning news on a 5-point Likert-type scale ranging from 1 (least satisfactory) to 5 (most satisfactory). Uses and gratifications reflected in items such as: "to apply data into my work and my daily life," "to widen my vision," and "to help seek for more knowledge in many aspects."

A convenience sampling was used to distribute a questionnaire to respondents, collecting data from undergraduate students at universities (both public and private), and in popular shopping malls in Bangkok. Totally, 400 usable questionnaires were received.

C. Data Analysis

The quantitative data was analyzed using SPSS/Windows 10.0 (Statistical Package for the Social Science). The statistics employed Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient and a univariate t-test.

IV. FINDINGS

The findings showed that information exposure of undergraduate students was at a high level ($M = 3.64$, $SD = 0.77$). Students' uses ($M = 3.51$, $SD = 0.57$) and gratifications ($M = 4.01$, $SD = 0.42$) were also at high level. Information exposure was positively correlated with uses ($r = 0.407$, $p < .01$), and gratifications ($r = .141$, $p < .01$). Uses of information were positively correlated with gratifications of television morning news ($r = 0.224$, $p < .01$). The results also revealed

that students with differences in sex were not significantly different in information exposure ($t = 0.023$, $p > .05$), uses of information ($t = 1.181$, $p > .05$), and gratifications ($t = 1.290$, $p > .05$). In addition, students with differences in type of university were not significantly different in information exposure ($t = 1.082$, $p > .05$), uses ($t = 0.910$, $p > .05$), and gratifications of television morning news ($t = 1.247$, $p > .05$).

V. DISCUSSION

The purposes of this study were to study and to investigate the relationship among exposure, uses and gratifications of television morning news among undergraduate students in Bangkok. This study also compared the students' group, who are of mixed gender, from different type of universities in Bangkok use the information from the television morning news differently and how. The results indicated that information exposure was positively correlated with uses and gratifications. Uses of information were positively correlated with satisfaction with information. Students with differences in sex and type of university were not significantly different in information exposure, and uses and gratifications. The results also showed that after watching television morning news, the students have applied the information into their works and their daily lives, widening their visions, and help them seek for more knowledge respectively.

Agreeing with Lamyong Duangkum [15], she studied about television viewing behaviors and the uses of television for teaching of private colleagues' faculties. The results showed that television viewing behaviors were correlated with the uses of television for teaching. Teachers with differences in sex, age, education, teaching experience, and faculty were not significantly different in using television programs for teaching. She also found that the factor that could adapt to the uses of televisions programs for teaching was exposure to news programs.

Concerning the uses and gratifications of television morning news, the results revealed that the more the students used the information, the more they were satisfied with the news. Consistent with Nantawan Kittanajaroen's study [16], she found that the uses of information were positively correlated with satisfaction with the information.

VI. SUGGESTIONS

The study shows that large numbers of students watch the television morning news; therefore the production team of the television morning news should be concerned about the needs to use and the gratifications of the audience. The study found that after watching the morning news, the audience has applied the data into their work and their daily life, widening their visions, and help the audience seek for more knowledge in many aspects accordingly. Thus, the content and the news presentation should be selected from the ones that help people gain knowledge with up to date news, in order to suit the needs of the audience.

VII. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE STUDIES

The limitations of this study are as follows:

1. The target group from this study was only chosen from students in Bangkok, as such, in the future there should be a study about the uses and gratifications about the television morning news from the undergraduate students from different regions of Thailand in order to know the comments that may vary in each region as a method to improve the content in making the television morning news in order that it can best meet the needs of the audience even more,
2. The future study should focus on more points, for example, the knowledge or the attitude of the audience, or to study about the content or the form of the news that audience wants. This can lead to the improvement of the television morning news and make it more qualified and better meet the genuine need of the audience, and
3. This study only considers television morning news in overview, so there should be a study that focuses on specific news programs, such as, the political news, economic news, social news etc. This is to understand about the media exposure, the usage, and the gratification of each aspect more clearly.

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